

Enhancing HTML Structure Comprehension: Real-Time 3D/XR Visualization of the DOM

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Abstract—Understanding the Document Object Model (DOM) is crucial for web development, yet traditional 2D representations can obscure the hierarchical complexity and spatial relationships of HTML elements. This paper introduces *babia-html*, a component of *BabiaXR*, which offers a novel approach to visualizing the DOM in 3D and XR for the web. Utilizing A-Frame, we develop a tool that provides real-time, three-dimensional representations of HTML structures. Additionally, we present a plugin for Visual Studio Code (VSCode) that integrates this 3D visualization directly into the development environment. Our goal is to explore how this visualization can enhance the comprehension of HTML structures, improve debugging processes, and facilitate more effective communication of structural changes within development teams. We outline the standalone capabilities of *babia-html*, its integration as a VSCode extension, and various use cases demonstrating its practical applications. This work provides preliminary insights into the potential benefits of 3D DOM visualization and its implications for modern web development practices, considering the potential impact on developer productivity and cognitive load, and proposing directions for future research and development. Video URL: <https://youtu.be/RFX2gblBNss>

Index Terms—extended reality, html, DOM, software visualization, web

I. INTRODUCTION

Web development relies heavily on understanding and manipulating the Document Object Model (DOM) [1], a hierarchical structure that represents the elements of an HTML document. Traditional 2D DOM visualizations can obscure complex nesting and spatial relationships within HTML documents, making it challenging for developers to efficiently debug and manage these structures. By leveraging 3D visualization, our approach offers a spatial representation of the DOM, providing a more intuitive understanding of the document’s architecture. This is particularly beneficial in identifying deeply nested elements and understanding the layout effects imposed by CSS and JavaScript, tasks that are cumbersome with 2D tools.

To address these challenges, we introduce *babia-html*, a component of *BabiaXR*, which leverages 3D and Extended Reality (XR) technologies to provide a real-time, three-dimensional visualization of the DOM within Visual Studio Code (VSCode). Utilizing A-Frame, an open-source framework for building WebXR [2] experiences, we have developed a tool that transforms the way developers interact with HTML structures. This tool not only enhances the comprehension of complex DOM hierarchies but also integrates seamlessly into the development workflow as a VSCode plugin.

The core idea behind this approach is to utilize 3D visualization to provide a more intuitive and comprehensive view of the DOM, thereby simplifying the process of debugging, navigating, and managing nested elements. By presenting the DOM in three dimensions, developers can quickly identify hierarchical relationships and spatial distributions that are often lost in 2D representations. This visualization technique aims to reduce cognitive load and improve overall productivity by making the structure and relationships within HTML documents more accessible and understandable.

Unlike existing tools such as *Tilt* [3] from Mozilla and Microsoft *3D View* [4] from Microsoft, which provide static 3D visualizations within browsers, *babia-html* uniquely integrates with an integrated development environment, offering real-time updates directly within the development environment. Additionally, *babia-html* leverages XR technologies to enhance developer interaction through immersive experiences that are not currently available in other tools.

In this paper, we present the design and implementation of *babia-html* and its integration into VSCode. We explore its standalone capabilities, its application as a VSCode extension, and various use cases demonstrating its practical benefits. Through these examples, we illustrate how 3D DOM visualization can transform web development practices, offering a new perspective that enhances both understanding and efficiency. Additionally, we discuss the potential impact on developer productivity and propose directions for future research and development in this area.

II. RELATED WORKS

Data visualization plays a crucial role in understanding complex information, particularly in software development and maintenance [5]. Traditionally, software repositories have been visualized using 2D graphical representations such as heatmaps, line charts, and bar charts [6], [7]. These methods, integrated into IDEs like Visual Studio Code and platforms like GitHub, help track changes and analyze code metrics over time [8]–[12]. Graphical tools enable developers to identify code quality issues and pinpoint hotspots that may require refactoring or additional testing [13].

As software systems become increasingly complex, the limitations of 2D visualizations become apparent, necessitating more advanced techniques. Virtual Reality (VR) has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing data visualization by leveraging multidimensionality. VR has been effectively used

in various domains such as brain tumor analysis [14], shape perception [15], paleontology [16], caves [17], and magnetic resonance imaging [18]. VR allows for immersive interaction with data, making abstract analysis more intuitive [19], [20].

Bryson [21] highlighted VR’s capabilities in handling complex data visualizations, though early critics like Munzner [22] and Few [23] warned against unjustified 3D use. Despite these concerns, researchers have argued for the benefits of 3D and VR visualizations. For example, Batch *et al.* [24] emphasized spatial use, Jacob *et al.* [25] focused on the embodiment of interfaces, and Rosenbaum *et al.* [26] on abstract involvement. In the aerospace engineering field, García-Hernández *et al.* [27] demonstrated the utility of VR.

The city metaphor has been a notable approach in VR visualizations for software architectures [28]. Initial concepts by Munro *et al.* [29] and the extensive work by Wettel *et al.* [30] led to the development of CityVR [31], which explored software dependencies and architectural visualization. Kobayashi *et al.* [32] and Yano *et al.* [33] expanded this metaphor to show dependencies between software packages. The *IslandViz* approach [34] further explored visualization of software architectures as islands, including package dependencies shown as relationships between islands and arrows representing the dependencies hierarchy.

We conducted an experiment comparing on-screen and VR versions of different visualizations [35], [36], which reinforced the potential of VR to enhance understanding and management of software structures. This paper aims to extend these concepts by evaluating the effectiveness of 3D DOM visualization in real-time within VSCode. By comparing traditional 2D tools with immersive VR visualizations, we seek to demonstrate the potential benefits of 3D visualizations for understanding and managing HTML structures in modern web development.

III. HTML IN 3D AND XR

In this section, we present the design and implementation of *babia-html* and its integration into VSCode. A replication package is publicly available¹ to reproduce the demos shown in this paper, along with instructions for installing the plugin and setup.

A. *babia-html* in a nutshell

babia-html is a component from *BabiaXR* [37]. *BabiaXR*² is a toolset for extended reality (including both AR and VR) data visualization in web browsers. It facilitates the definition of data visualization scenes by automating and generalizing the most common tasks. It is based on *A-Frame*³, a JavaScript framework to build 3D, augmented reality (AR), and VR scenes in the browser. *babia-html* is a visualizer component that provides three-dimensional representations of HTML structures.

¹Replication Package: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13259502>

²*BabiaXR* source code: <https://gitlab.com/babiaxr/aframe-babia-components>

³*A-Frame*: <https://aframe.io>

babia-html renders the DOM in 3D, allowing developers to see the hierarchical structure of an HTML document in a more intuitive and comprehensive manner. The visualization displays each element as a box within the 3D scene, with the spatial arrangement reflecting the parent-child relationships in the DOM tree.

To enhance usability, *babia-html* includes interactive buttons that allow users to collapse and expand the boxes representing elements. This functionality helps developers to focus on specific sections of the DOM tree and understand the inheritance and nesting more clearly. By collapsing less relevant parts of the tree, users can reduce visual clutter and concentrate on the elements of interest.

Moreover, the children elements within the DOM tree are rendered with textures that visually represent their HTML content. This feature aids users in quickly identifying and understanding the nested structure of the HTML, making it easier to see how different elements are related and how they fit within the overall hierarchy. The texture rendering provides a visual cue that helps to differentiate between various types of elements and their roles within the document.

In addition to the 3D visualization, *babia-html* includes VR and AR (collectively referred to as XR) capabilities. This allows developers to immerse themselves in the visualization using XR devices, with the goal of utilizing this visualization in real-time alongside an IDE, as we explain in the next section. This immersive experience can further enhance the understanding and management of complex DOM structures.

Finally, if the HTML being visualized has other JavaScript or CSS dependencies that alter the layout of the final HTML, *babia-html* takes these into account. The visualization shows the final rendered HTML with the current layout displayed on the screen, including the effects of any JavaScript and CSS. This ensures that the visualization accurately reflects the actual appearance and structure of the HTML as it would be seen in a web browser. Developers can use 3D visualization to easily debug complex CSS layouts by visualizing how styles affect nested elements in real-time. The spatial representation helps identify issues such as overlapping elements or unexpected behavior caused by CSS rules, which are not readily apparent in 2D views. One full example is shown in Figure 1

B. Real-time: VSCode Extension

An essential part of our implementation is the availability of a VSCode extension that facilitates real-time 3D visualization of HTML structures directly within the development environment. This open-source plugin, available for download⁴, allows developers to see a 3D representation of the HTML document currently open in the editor. As changes are made to the HTML code, the visualization updates in real time, providing immediate feedback and a dynamic view of the document’s structure.

This real-time visualization is particularly useful in a multi-monitor setup augmented with AR glasses. For instance, a

⁴Marketplace: <https://marketplace.visualstudio.com/items?itemName=dumbrr.html-in-xr>

Fig. 1: 3D DOM visualization of *babia-html* from a complex HTML document. Showing the rendered HTML with the current layout displayed on the screen, including the effects of CSS. Buttons for rotating and collapsing/expanding the DOM tree are shown on the top side of the scene.

developer can work with two monitors: one displaying the raw HTML code and the other showing the rendered HTML in a web browser. Simultaneously, with the AR glasses, the developer can view the 3D visualization of the DOM, which updates in real time as the code changes. This setup allows for a seamless and integrated workflow where the spatial relationships and hierarchical structure of the DOM can be continuously monitored and understood without switching contexts. An example of this setup is shown in Figure 2

Fig. 2: Setup with AR glasses, two monitors, and real-time 3D DOM visualization.

By using this plugin, developers can gain a deeper understanding of the HTML structure they are working with, quickly identify issues, and improve their productivity. The ability to visualize the DOM in 3D in real time, combined with the immersive experience provided by AR glasses, represents a significant advancement in web development tools, enhancing both the comprehension and management of complex HTML documents.

IV. USE CASES

We present two examples of HTML structures that illustrate the advantages of using 3D DOM visualization. These

examples demonstrate how a three-dimensional perspective can enhance the comprehension of the hierarchical and spatial relationships within the document.

Example 1: Moderate Structure The first example features a moderately complex HTML structure. This structure includes a header with a title and a navigation menu, a main content area with a section and an article, and a footer.

Listing 1: Moderate HTML structure with multiple levels of nesting

```
<header>
  <h1>Website Title</h1>
  <nav>
    <ul>
      <li><a href='#home'>Home</a></li>
      <li><a href='#about'>About</a></li>
      <li><a href='#contact'>Contact</a></li>
    </ul>
  </nav>
</header>
<main>
  <section>
    <h2>Main Content</h2>
    <article>
      <h3>Article Title</h3>
      <p>Article content goes here.</p>
    </article>
    <aside>
      <h4>Related Links</h4>
      <ul>
        <li><a href='#link1'>Link 1</a></li>
        <li><a href='#link2'>Link 2</a></li>
      </ul>
    </aside>
  </section>
</main>
<footer>
  <p>\&copy; 2024 Website</p>
</footer>
```

In this example, the 3D visualization helps developers quickly identify the hierarchical structure of the document. Elements like the navigation menu and the related links within the main content section are more intuitively understood in a three-dimensional space, making it easier to see how they fit into the overall structure of the webpage. This can be particularly beneficial for debugging and ensuring that elements are correctly nested and displayed.

Example 2: Complex Structure The second example showcases a more complex HTML structure, including a navigation with dropdown menus, introduction and feature sections, a highlighted article with a table, and a footer.

Listing 2: Complex HTML structure with multiple levels of nesting and various types of content

```
<div class='wrapper'>
  <header>
    <div class='branding'>
      <h1>Brand Name</h1>
      <nav>
        <ul>
          <li><a href='#home'>Home</a></li>
          <li><a href='#products'>Products</a>
            <ul>
              <li><a href='#product1'>Product 1</a></li>
              <li><a href='#product2'>Product 2</a></li>
            </ul>
          </li>
          <li><a href='#services'>Services</a></li>
          <li><a href='#contact'>Contact</a></li>
        </ul>
      </nav>
    </div>
  </header>
  <main>
    <section class='intro'>
      <h2>Welcome</h2>
      <p>Introduction content here.</p>
```

```

</section>
<section class='features'>
  <div class='feature'>
    <h3>Feature 1</h3>
    <p>Description of feature 1.</p>
  </div>
  <div class='feature'>
    <h3>Feature 2</h3>
    <p>Description of feature 2.</p>
  </div>
</section>
<article class='highlight'>
  <h2>Highlighted Article</h2>
  <p>Content of the highlighted article.</p>
  <table>
    <thead>
      <tr>
        <th>Column 1</th>
        <th>Column 2</th>
        <th>Column 3</th>
      </tr>
    </thead>
    <tbody>
      <tr>
        <td>Data 1</td>
        <td>Data 2</td>
        <td>Data 3</td>
      </tr>
      <tr>
        <td>Data 4</td>
        <td>Data 5</td>
        <td>Data 6</td>
      </tr>
    </tbody>
  </table>
</article>
</main>
<footer>
  <p>\&copy; 2024 Company Name</p>
</footer>
</div>

```


(a) HTML in Listing 2 rendered in a browser

(b) HTML in Listing 2 rendered in 3D

Fig. 4: DOM rendered in a browser (top) and in 3D (below) of code presented in Listing 2.

In this complex example, the benefits of 3D visualization are even more pronounced. The hierarchical relationships, such as the nested navigation menus and the various sections within the main content area, are more easily understood in a three-dimensional space. The table within the highlighted article adds another layer of complexity, and a 3D view helps in visualizing the spatial distribution of table elements relative to other content. This not only aids in debugging and verifying the correct structure but also improves the overall comprehension of the document layout.

By utilizing 3D DOM visualization, developers can gain a more intuitive and comprehensive understanding of the HTML document's structure. This approach helps in identifying issues, understanding nested relationships, and managing complex layouts more effectively than traditional 2D representations.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The 3D visualization of the DOM provided by *babia-html* is an advancement in the field of web development tools. Traditional 2D representations of the DOM often fail to convey

Website Title

- [Home](#)
- [About](#)
- [Contact](#)

Main Content

Article Title

Article content goes here.

Related Links

- [Link 1](#)
- [Link 2](#)

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(a) HTML in Listing 1 rendered in a browser

(b) HTML in Listing 1 rendered in 3D

Fig. 3: DOM rendered in a browser (top) and in 3D (below) of code presented in Listing 1.

the complexity and hierarchical nature of HTML documents. By visualizing the DOM in three dimensions, developers can gain a more intuitive and comprehensive understanding of the structure and relationships within their HTML code. This enhanced understanding can lead to more efficient debugging, easier navigation through complex structures, and a better grasp of the document's overall architecture. The ability to see the spatial relationships and nesting of elements at a glance reduces cognitive load and speeds up the identification of structural issues.

While tools like Mozilla's *Tilt* and Microsoft's *3D View* have demonstrated the potential of 3D visualization in enhancing web development, *babia-html* distinguishes itself by integrating these capabilities directly into the development workflow through VSCode. *Tilt* was an innovative Firefox extension that provided a 3D representation of web pages to assist with inspection, navigation, and debugging. Similarly, *3D View* in Microsoft Edge offers a way to visualize web page layers and the DOM in three dimensions to facilitate debugging. However, both of these tools operate within the browser environment, which requires developers to switch contexts between coding and visualization. *babia-html* enhances this experience by providing real-time updates that align with code edits within Visual Studio Code. This integration allows developers to observe the immediate impact of their changes without leaving the development environment, thereby streamlining their workflow. Additionally, the XR capabilities of *babia-html* offer an immersive experience where developers can interact with the DOM in augmented reality, providing a novel way to bridge the gap between abstract code and its concrete execution. This immersive environment allows developers to visualize the DOM as a spatial structure, where elements are naturally grouped and displayed in relation to one another, offering insights into their hierarchical dependencies and interactions.

Moreover, this tool can be particularly beneficial for HTML beginners. Learning HTML can be challenging, especially when dealing with nested elements and understanding their relationships. A 3D visualization can make these concepts more accessible, providing a clear and interactive way to explore and learn HTML. This could significantly enhance the learning experience for newcomers, helping them to understand the structure and logic of HTML more quickly and effectively. By visualizing how elements nest within each other and how they interact spatially, beginners can develop a more robust mental model of how HTML works.

The integration of AR for real-time visualization represents a groundbreaking development in HTML writing and editing. By using AR glasses, developers can immerse themselves in the 3D representation of the DOM while simultaneously working on the code. This immersive experience can bridge the gap between the abstract code and its concrete structure, providing continuous, real-time feedback. This integration could revolutionize how developers write and understand HTML, making the process more interactive and engaging. Imagine a development environment where you can see the live DOM

structure floating beside your code editor, making it easier to track changes and understand the impact of your edits in real time.

The immersive experience provided by *babia-html* aims to reduce cognitive load by allowing developers to view the DOM structure spatially, similar to how it appears in a browser. This approach not only enhances comprehension but aims to improve debugging efficiency. Future work will focus on validating *babia-html* with practitioners, conducting empirical studies to measure its impact on developer productivity and learning outcomes, and continuously improving the tool based on feedback and study findings to enhance its usability and functionality.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. W. W. Consortium *et al.*, "Document object model (dom) level 3 core specification," 2004.
- [2] B. Jones and M. Goregaokar, "WebXR device API," W3C Working Draft, Jul. 2020.
- [3] "Debugging and editing webpages in 3D – Mozilla Hacks - the Web developer blog — hacks.mozilla.org," <https://hacks.mozilla.org/2011/10/debugging-and-editing-webpages-in-3d/>, [Accessed 07-08-2024].
- [4] MSEdgeTeam, "Navigate webpage layers, z-index, and DOM using the 3D View tool - Microsoft Edge Developer documentation — learn.microsoft.com," <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-edge/devtools-guide-chromium/3d-view/>, [Accessed 07-08-2024].
- [5] R. Koschke, "Software visualization in software maintenance, reverse engineering, and re-engineering: a research survey," *Journal of Software Maintenance and Evolution: Research and Practice*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 87–109, 2003.
- [6] T. Ball and S. G. Eick, "Software visualization in the large," *Computer*, vol. 29, no. 4, p. 33–43, apr 1996. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/2.488299>
- [7] M. Lanza and R. Marinescu, *Object-oriented metrics in practice: using software metrics to characterize, evaluate, and improve the design of object-oriented systems*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2007.
- [8] A. Bacchelli and C. Bird, "Expectations, outcomes, and challenges of modern code review," in *2013 35th ICSE*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 712–721.
- [9] P. Thongtanunam, S. McIntosh, A. E. Hassan, and H. Iida, "Review participation in modern code review," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 768–817, 2017.
- [10] Y. Yu, H. Wang, V. Filkov, P. Devanbu, and B. Vasilescu, "Wait for it: Determinants of pull request evaluation latency on github," in *2015 IEEE/ACM 12th working conference on mining software repositories*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 367–371.
- [11] T. Fritz, J. Ou, G. C. Murphy, and E. Murphy-Hill, "A degree-of-knowledge model to capture source code familiarity," in *Proceedings of the 32nd ACM/IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering - Volume 1*, ser. ICSE '10. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2010, p. 385–394. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1806799.1806856>
- [12] A. Bachmann, C. Bird, F. Rahman, P. Devanbu, and A. Bernstein, "The missing links: bugs and bug-fix commits," in *Proceedings of the Eighteenth ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering*, ser. FSE '10. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2010, p. 97–106. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1882291.1882308>
- [13] B. Meyer, "Seven principles of software testing," *Computer*, vol. 41, no. 8, pp. 99–101, 2008.
- [14] S. Zhang, C. Demiralp, D. Keefe, M. DaSilva, D. Laidlaw, B. Greenberg, P. Basser, C. Pierpaoli, E. Chiocca, and T. Deisboeck, "An immersive virtual environment for dt-mri volume visualization applications: a case study," in *Proceedings Visualization, 2001. VIS '01.*, 2001, pp. 437–584.
- [15] C. Demiralp, C. Jackson, D. Karelitz, S. Zhang, and D. Laidlaw, "Cave and fishtank virtual-reality displays: A qualitative and quantitative comparison," *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, vol. 12, pp. 323–30, 05 2006.
- [16] B. Laha, D. Bowman, and J. Socha, "Effects of vr system fidelity on analyzing isosurface visualization of volume datasets," *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, vol. 20, pp. 513–22, 04 2014.

- [17] E. D. Ragan, R. Kopper, P. Schuchardt, and D. A. Bowman, "Studying the effects of stereo, head tracking, and field of regard on a small-scale spatial judgment task," *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 886–896, 2013.
- [18] J. J. Chen, H. Cai, A. P. Auchus, and D. H. Laidlaw, "Effects of stereo and screen size on the legibility of three-dimensional streamtube visualization," *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, vol. 18, pp. 2130–2139, 2012.
- [19] P. Milgram and F. Kishino, "A taxonomy of mixed reality visual displays," *IEICE TRANSACTIONS on Information and Systems*, vol. 77, no. 12, pp. 1321–1329, 1994.
- [20] R. Skarbez, M. Smith, and M. C. Whitton, "Revisiting milgram and kishino's reality-virtuality continuum," *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*, vol. 2, p. 647997, 2021.
- [21] S. Bryson, "Virtual reality in scientific visualization," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 62–71, 1996.
- [22] T. Munzner, *Visualization analysis and design*. CRC press, 2014.
- [23] S. Few, "Show me the numbers," *Analytics Pres*, 2004.
- [24] A. Batch, A. Cunningham, M. Cordeil, N. Elmquist, T. Dwyer, B. H. Thomas, and K. Marriott, "There is no spoon: Evaluating performance, space use, and presence with expert domain users in immersive analytics," *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 536–546, 2019.
- [25] R. J. Jacob, A. Girouard, L. M. Hirshfield, M. S. Horn, O. Shaer, E. T. Solovey, and J. Zigelbaum, "Reality-based interaction: a framework for post-wimp interfaces," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems*, 2008, pp. 201–210.
- [26] R. Rosenbaum, J. Bottleson, Z. Liu, and B. Hamann, "Involve me and i will understand!—abstract data visualization in immersive environments," in *International Symposium on Visual Computing*. Springer, 2011, pp. 530–540.
- [27] R. J. García-Hernández, C. Anthes, M. Wiedemann, and D. Kranzlmüller, "Perspectives for using virtual reality to extend visual data mining in information visualization," in *2016 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2016, pp. 1–11.
- [28] D. Moreno-Lumbreras, J. M. Gonzalez-Barahona, G. Robles, and V. Cosentino, "The influence of the city metaphor and its derivatives in software visualization," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 210, p. 111985, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0164121224000281>
- [29] C. Knight and M. Munro, "Comprehension with[in] virtual environment visualisations," in *Proceedings Seventh International Workshop on Program Comprehension*, 1999, pp. 4–11.
- [30] R. Wetzel and M. Lanza, "Visualizing software systems as cities," in *2007 4th IEEE International Workshop on Visualizing Software for Understanding and Analysis*, 2007, pp. 92–99.
- [31] L. Merino, M. Ghafari, C. Anslow, and O. Nierstrasz, "CityVR: Gameful software visualization," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution (ICSME)*, 2017, pp. 633–637.
- [32] K. Kobayashi, M. Kamimura, K. Yano, K. Kato, and A. Matsuo, "Sarf map: Visualizing software architecture from feature and layer viewpoints," in *2013 21st International Conference on Program Comprehension (ICPC)*, 2013, pp. 43–52.
- [33] K. Yano and A. Matsuo, "Data access visualization for legacy application maintenance," in *2017 IEEE 24th International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering (SANER)*, 2017, pp. 546–550.
- [34] M. Misiak, A. Schreiber, A. Fuhrmann, S. Zur, D. Seider, and L. Nafeie, "IslandViz: A tool for visualizing modular software systems in virtual reality," in *2018 IEEE Working Conference on Software Visualization (VISSOFT)*, 2018, pp. 112–116.
- [35] D. Moreno-Lumbreras, R. Minelli, A. Villaverde, J. M. Gonzalez-Barahona, and M. Lanza, "Codecity: A comparison of on-screen and virtual reality," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 153, p. 107064, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584922001732>
- [36] D. Moreno-Lumbreras, G. Robles, D. Izquierdo-Cortázar, and J. M. Gonzalez-Barahona, "Software development metrics: to vr or not to vr," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 2, p. 42, Feb 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-023-10435-3>
- [37] D. Moreno-Lumbreras, J. M. Gonzalez-Barahona, and A. Villaverde, "BabiaXR: Virtual reality software data visualizations for the web," in *2022 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 71–74.